

STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT OF THE MARKETING CONCEPT

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Abstract: In the article, the development of the marketing concept is divided into stages, and its main ideas, goals and tools are considered.

The marketing concept is developed on the basis of a strategic analysis of planned and implemented business activities. When developing a marketing concept, attention is paid to:

- Implementation of strategic analysis of internal and external environment;
- Determining marketing activities and farming objectives;
- Selection of elements of marketing activities in order to achieve planned results.

The concept of marketing has passed the stage of evolutionary development in terms of its dependence on the level of development of demand for production and offered goods. The following figure and table provide details about the marketing concept.

Figure 1.1 Marketing concept.

World science and practice in the field of marketing and entrepreneurship based and recommended the following concepts in marketing evaluation:

- ❖ production concept;
- ❖ brand concept;
- ❖ sales concept;
- ❖ traditional marketing concept;
- ❖ concept of socio-ethical marketing;
- ❖ the concept of interactive marketing.

1. Table 1

Years	Concept	The main idea	The main tool	The main purpose
1860-1920	Production	Production as much as possible	Cost, labor productivity	Improvement of production, increase of sales volume
1920-1930	Goods	Production of quality goods	Product policy	Improving the properties of consumer goods
1930-1950	Selling	Development of sales networks and channels	Sales Policy	Product sales intensification
1960-1980	Traditional marketing	Production of consumer goods	Marketing mix complex, consumer research	Research the needs of the target market
1980-1995	Social and moral marketing	Production of goods needed by consumers, taking into account the demands of society	Research the social and environmental consequences of the marketing mix complex, the production of goods and services, and the consumer.	Meeting the needs of the target market
since 1995 until s hu	The interactive concept of marketing	Production of goods that satisfy business partners and consumers	Marketing mix complex, integration and network analysis , coordination style	Meeting the needs of the target market

The marketing concept presented should not be considered as a standard or norm or rule for each country. Marketing evaluation in each country depends on its characteristics and the level of development of market relations in a country. However, the world experience related to the emergence of marketing and the development of

market relations can be used to shape the market relations of the implementation of entrepreneurial activities in a country. is considered useful. In addition, the well-known general trend in the development of marketing is to shift attention from the production of goods to the consumer, his wishes and needs.

The first period - the marketing concept is defined in the style of "production concept" - "product superiority", where the most important issue is to produce good goods and sell them to consumers at low prices. Concept slogan - "produce as many goods as possible, because the market demand is unlimited"

The concept of the product requires the attention of the consumer to be focused on the product, its quality and price. Consumers compare the quality of similar goods with similar goods of another firm. This concept is often held by companies, firms, organizations, but the product concept does not bring success.

The next period was named "sales concept". In this case, the goal of selling the company's products under the slogan "here is the ready product, come and bargain" comes first. The concepts of product and trade marketing came into play at a time when product production had not yet become mass-produced. High profits were made by new types and varieties of goods, because the demand for these goods was insanely high in a market with essentially unlimited demand.

In the 50s, the first basis of the management concept was analyzed to determine the long-term changes in sales volume, the level of production and transaction costs, income, profit and other indicators. Accordingly, it was planned to adjust the performance in the market from one to five years. .

The 50s of the last century was an important stage in the history of marketing development. The problem of overproduction became apparent. Marketing - the concept of adapting production to market demand, its basis was targeting the consumer - "market advantage".

The traditional marketing concept has become a leading role in management in the form of the marketing market concept, which determines not only the market strategy, but also the production strategy of the company since the mid-50s of the last century. Marketing service has become the main management center of the company, a source of information and recommendations on issues of market, production, scientific-technical and financial activities. Marketing service solves the issues of the necessity, perspective and usefulness of production of a product, possibilities of

providing production programs from the material and technical aspects, based on a detailed analysis of changes in social demand and market conditions.

The image below shows the concept of sales and marketing.

Sales (commercial) concept

Marketing concept

1.2 - picture. Sales and marketing concept .

By the 60s of the 20th century, the issue of implementing strategic planning based on market changes was put forward and resolved.

By the 70s of the last century, such a concept of marketing was developed that it freely entered the life of economically developed countries.

The country has taken a central place in the internal activities of economic entities as a whole organism and in planning within the firm. It is a new form of strategic management focused on the market economy, which continuously distributes goods from producers to consumers in order to obtain the most profit.

Many productions were started, with the appearance and technology of the products being partially changed. The main form of competition has become price competition. Therefore, in the following years, a constant struggle to reduce costs and introduce effective technologies has become a key to success.

The concept of social ethical marketing - this concept considers that the task of the firm is to study, analyze the needs of individuals and effectively satisfy these needs, while at the same time maintaining and strengthening the integrity of the society as a whole. The concept of socio-ethical marketing, compared to the market concept of management, appeared at a time when there were growing doubts about the relevance of this program to our times due to the growing environmental problems, lack of natural resources, global inflation, and the strange situation of social service sectors.

Initially, the company's activity in market relations is mainly focused on profit. Later, they realized the strategic importance of meeting customer needs, and as a result, the concept of market marketing was born. Today, they start thinking about the interests of the society before doing any important work. Socio-ethical marketing requires market participants to consider three factors in the framework of marketing policy in relation to each other, these factors are company profit, customer needs and the interests of society. This is illustrated in Figure 1.3 below.

Figure 1.3 Factors influencing the concept of social ethical marketing

the interactive concept of marketing is the relationship (communication) between buyers and other participants of the buying and selling process. Marketing interaction increases the importance of effective communication, personal interactions. Relationship marketing sees communication in a broader sense as the desired interaction between a company and its partners that generates income.

The process of sales, and then marketing, in the industry is considered to be a characteristic of the transition economy. Marketing evolution is observed with changes in marketing concept, form and elements. Below we will get acquainted with the theoretical foundations, methods, and areas of application of marketing evaluation.

1. 2 - table

Marketing evaluation as a science

Years	Theoretical foundations	Styles	Field of application
1900-1950s	Learning about the product, targeting distribution, sales and export theory	Tracking, analysis of buyers and sales, calculation of probabilities, consumption panel	Mass goods production, agricultural sector
1960	Learning about sales, sales volume targeting, dispersal theory	Applying motivation, activity, modeling	Consumers of consumer goods
1970	Scientific foundations of decision-making and behavior	Factor, discriminant analysis, consumer typology, expertise, cause-effect analysis	Consumers of means of production and consumer goods
1980-1990 years	Situational analysis, learning about marketing as a management function, competitive analysis theory, ecological basics, strategic marketing	Positioning, cluster analysis, consumer typology, expertise, cause and effect analysis	Consumers of consumer goods, means of production, service industry, non-profit organizations
1990 to the present	Learning about marketing as a business tool and function, market network theory, targeting social and environmental performance	Positioning, cluster analysis, consumer typology, competitor and consumer behavior models, benchmark marketing, game theory	Means of production, means of consumption, service industry, non-profit organizations, consumers in the

			field of state entrepreneurship
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Marketing concept is a management philosophy. And it helps the producers of the goods to satisfy the needs of the consumers so that they can benefit in the long run:

- activation of business activity;
- influence the market;
- to target groups of consumers;
- it is necessary to draw attention to the main strategic goal.

In conclusion, it can be said that the concept of Marketing has been interpreted in different ways in different periods and views have changed over time. The current modern marketing concept has been forming since the 90s of the last century .

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